

EVENTS TRADITIONAL AND TRANSFORMATIVE VOCAL
PROCEDURES

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Annotation: The article will help to study the history of vocal spirituality in our country, to study the rich national and spiritual heritage on the basis of sacred sites, to conduct a comprehensive study of the sacred places of thus to gain a deeper understanding of the rich aspects of our spiritual history.

Key words: Modern play, Asian culture, vocal, country.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada mamlakatimizdagi vokal ma'naviyati tarixini o'rganishga, muqaddas joylar asosidagi boy milliy-ma'naviy merosni o'rganishga, mamlakatimizdagi muqaddas maskanlarni har tomonlama o'rganishga, shu orqali ustozlardan bizgacha yetib kelgan merosni chuqurroq anglashga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Zamonaviy o'yinlar, Osiyo madaniyati, vokal, mamlakat.

Аннотация: Статья поможет изучить историю вокальной духовности в нашей стране, изучить богатое национальное и духовное наследие на основе сакральных мест, тем самым получить более глубокое представление о богатых аспектах нашей духовной истории.

Ключевые слова: Современная пьеса, азиатская культура, вокал, страна.

Like all other nations of the world, the Uzbek people are entering the 21st century with great confidence and hope. The whole world recognizes that our territory, now called Uzbekistan, is one of the cradles of not only the East but also of the world civilization. It was a sacred site of various cultures and religions, with a very diverse region of religions, cultures and lifestyles. The fact that the territory of our country at the same time was supposed to have been the first inhabited earth, and a number of

evidences concerning, show the ancient history of this land. Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions, which are the southern oasis of Uzbekistan, are also a rich «ethnographic center» of centuries-old material and spiritual heritage. Because these lands are geographically subdivided into mountains and steppes. This is the area where the traditions and customs of the settled and nomadic population are in harmony.

It should be noted that the southern pilgrimages of Uzbekistan can be divided into local and national shrines, depending on their location. The first group of republican pilgrims is Langar-ota (Kamashi district), Hazrati Bashir (Kitab district), Hodja Ubaydo Jarrah (Karshi city), Termez ota (Termez district), Sultan Saodat (Termez district), forty girls (Termez district). The second group is Necca Said ota, Tutak-ota, Qirbulbuloq ota (Yakkabog district), Old Fazli and Mirhaydar Sultan. (Kasbi district), Arslanbob (Shakhrisabz t TAL), Kuls koy (District), Saad ibn Abi Waqqas (Angor district), Xo'jamuqon (Sherobod district), Sugar (Bandikhon district), clothing (Oltinsoy district) places the local places.

According to the custom of pilgrimage, pilgrims were always treated with special humility. During the visit, the locals tried to find answers to their troubles, and for a time the world was freed from the anxiety of the world and the soul was relieved. They tried to reason with the spirits of the saints secretly. In addition, sick people sought treatment through various visits. The local's attitude towards the shrines was positive, and everyone passing by the pilgrims, shrines got off if they were in traffic and then went on their way.

On certain days of the week among the locals in the southern oasis of Uzbekistan, certain days of the week, especially on Wednesdays and Saturdays, are the most pleasant days, ie the days of pilgrimage. Because these days, people are known to be the most prosperous. Most of the pilgrims are people who are always in a difficult situation, as well as unhappy young men, families with no children, who want to give thanks or when things go wrong, but also those who come to thank. The majority of visitors are women. As a result of our fieldwork in the southern regions of Uzbekistan,

it was found that men who wore headscarves in front of all pilgrims in the area were wearing headscarves without respect for the pilgrimage before entering the shrine.

The analysis of many rituals in the shrines shows that some of the rituals are related to pre-Islamic beliefs. For example, we can see the unusual connection with the saints here in the conversion of the tombs and tombs, the pursuit of dialogue, and the ritual connection between the visitor and the object of worship, and the combination of Islamic and pre-Islamic beliefs.

In Central Asia, including the southern regions of Uzbekistan, the shrines of the saints are often a place of pilgrimage, but sometimes also a place where people of different nationalities and nations interact and interact with each other. Many locals may witness the interethnic relations at the Termez Fathers, Hazrati Bashir and Langar Ata sites, which are regularly visited all week. The majority of pilgrims are representatives of various nationalities in the city and suburbs.

The people have come to visit the shrines as sacred places of healing for various diseases. For the reason, each pilgrimage site is distinguished by the specific nature of the disease. For example, it is the Tutakota shrine in the Tutak village of Yakkabag district, whose name is Shodi Sheikh. Young children with "cough" are usually brought here. At the entrance to the shrine, there was a boulder, which was taken from the spring water and poured over the slope of the rock. The water went down to a special container. This condition was repeated three times and the child was given a drink. According to local residents, they were cured. In addition, the water and soils of the shrines that treat various wounds and sugars in the body are generally regarded as curative. For example, the soil under the sacred Kushchalishota tomb in the Kamashi village cemetery in Kasbi district is consecrated by the local people and is considered to have divine treatment. Pilgrims come here to seek healing for the disease, take soil beneath the grave, mix it with water on the bedside, and drag it to the

ground, saying, "This is his name." According to them, after a while, the uranium disappeared.¹

There are also numerous natural springs in the southern regions of Uzbekistan and their waters are considered to be healing. An example of this is the Kurtbulak father's shrine. This pilgrimage is located in Yakkabag district, where the locals usually visit on Wednesdays and Fridays. A field survey revealed that the majority of visitors were mothers with young children. Here they go for a cure for a skin disease known as "Chilla". It is a skin disorder that occurs in the chill of the infants, which often covers the upper parts of the body. Also, Chile's popularity to protect her and her mother from the influence of sex depends on how they follow the Chilean period (which means chill-Persian "chill"). Chile is the term that represents the most dangerous, the most difficult times in human life.² According to local people, it is "Ikhlos-salad", and they say that if they come here sincerely, they will get well.³ Infertility and infertility cemeteries are also common in the southern oasis of Uzbekistan. Examples include Nazarbaba (Kasbi District), Mecca Saidota, Tutak-ota (Yakkabog District). According to the locals, these sacred graves are believed to have had a maternal happiness if children visit it with devotion. Most of the visitors to Nazarbaba's shrine in the area are mostly female children. If the bride has had no children for many years, she has come here and tied her head scarf to the special tree in the shrine. If the bride is pregnant within a reasonable period of time, she will come back for a second time and "get out". The expulsion was seen as agreeing with the spirit of the saint, who is present here among the locals. To that end, they were able to bring a cock, a goat or a sheep, depending on their circumstances and cook it and share it with those who came. According to the locals, the more people eat, the greater the reward.⁴

¹ Дала таджикотлари. Касби тумани, Камаги кишлоги, 2012 й.

² Аширов А.А. Узбек халкининг эътикод ва маросимлар. Т., 2007 й. 79 б.

³ Дала таджикотлари. Яккабоғ тумани. 2011 й.

⁴ Дала таджикотлари. Нишон тумани. Мерганча кишлоги. 2012 й.

According to the informant, every person who came to visit had sacrificed chicken or cock, sheep and goat. Some of that creature was cooked and eaten there. He donated the rest to the sheikhs of the cemetery by baking them.⁵ Sacrifice in Arabic meant to approach God, that is, to sacrifice the way of God to gain His mercy. In the earliest times, many peoples, including pre-Islamic Arabs, used to sacrifice slaves and their children. Over the years, the habit of sacrificing a human has become the habit of sacrificing an animal. According to the Quran, when Abraham decided to sacrifice his son Ishmael, Allah ordered him to stop and slaughter a ram instead of a baby.⁶ They sacrificed sheep, cattle and camels. When they make a sacrifice, those who intend to do so feel as though they are free from all ill feelings. At the same time, baked ham, as well as steamed. The bride arrived last time at the end of the ceremony, took off her scarf and took it with her.

Apart from these habits, pilgrims also have customs and practices related to the threshold of women's participation. When the pilgrims came to the shrines, they swept the tomb. Sweeping is a form of expression of desire and desire, which is a tradition of our people. For example, pilgrims who came to the Old Fazli Cemetery in Mirishkor District had swept the area around the site, which was a good tradition for them. Sweeping the threshold of the royal palace in the fairy tales and legends means that the princesses have come to the bridegroom, and sweeping the sacred graves means asking for help from the saints. Some pilgrims have taken over the grave after sweeping the cemetery, claiming to have had various skin diseases. The water from the holy graves was sprinkled on the threshold, "Let the trouble come." It seems to us that these views, in turn, are based on the ideas of respecting and honoring ancestors. In particular, the idea of asking these ancestors to help sweep the threshold is evident. Therefore, threshold soil is also thought to have magical power. It was thought that the holy graves had been blessed by the saints. Therefore, the soil, which is considered to be of healing

⁵ Дала тадкикотлари. Шахрисабз тумани. 2011 й.

⁶ Ислом энциклопедияси. Зухриддин Хусниддинов тахрири остида. «Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси» Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2004 й. 295 б.

properties because of its inherent properties, may be wounded on the hands and body, and the people who are interrogated will take it from their soil and take it home. They also give alms for their land.⁷ At the same time in many cases, childless women swept around the grave and asked for children. These include Nazarbakho in Nishan district of Kashkadarya oasis, Tutakota in Yakkabag district, and Rozhiboy Ahun in Kasbi district. It may be argued that the importance of the threshold in the sacred shrines and the reason why the threshold is elevated to the cult is, according to L. Hamdamova, "According to mythological views, the threshold serves as a border of two worlds. The genesis of the cult of Astana is linked to the mythological notions of good and evil places."⁸ We have also learned from the scientific research that among the inhabitants of the oasis, the saying "Don't sit in Astana, you will be unhappy" is not in vain. In addition, unhappy girls take a broom and sweep them to the shrine. Near the shrine, there was a chillah, in ancient times some pilgrims were forty days chained and purified.

In addition, ritual binding was also practiced in the Southern Uzbekistan oasis with the participation of women. If they were trees around sacred graves, they tied rags to them. According to our Tree Ribbon Towers, anyone who walks past the sacred trees should stop and rest for a while and tie the ribbon to the tree. Then the fatigue in that person will disappear. It was believed that if he did not do so he would be misled and would eventually die. We believe that tying rags to trees in sacred graves is a symbolic link between a visitor and a sacred place, and every visitor expresses their wishes and wishes by tying rags. G. Snesev commented on this as "the establishment of a magical link between the holy place and the visitor."⁹ Tying rags to the branches of a tree in Turkic nations is an example of sacrificing to spirits. Failure to do so may result in injury to the sponsored spirit. According to local residents, women are usually

⁷ Дала таджикотлари. Кашкадарё вилояти. Шахрисабз тумани. Темирчи кишлоги. 2012 й.

⁸ Хамдамова С. Фуркат лирикасида остона образи// Узбек тили ва адабиёти. 2003. №5. 63 б.

⁹ Снесарев Р.П. Хорезмские легенды как источник по истории религиозных культов Средней Азии. С-36.

to a tree branch for some reason. If his plans were to be fulfilled, they would go to that shrine and offer sacrifices and make fun.

The pilgrim also showed hope and confidence in the holy place by tying the rags. When his wish came true, he took off his robe for the second time and sacrificed to the tomb. This is typical of the peoples of Central Asia, including Ch.Ch. Valihanov writes: "All the extraordinary nature of nature, such as a desert tree and a beautiful plant with branches, was considered sacred and served as a pilgrimage. Each passenger tied a tree or a piece of cloth to that tree and presented the animal as a sacrifice." ¹⁰ It is said that a person who has come here three or seven times will achieve whatever he asks of God. Regardless of the attitude of Islam to these practices, these are customs that have been preserved from the ancient times and supposedly religious. It is a long-standing tradition of our people to ask God for their intentions by visiting the shrines of great scholars and saints. In doing so, they follow the words of the Prophet regarding visiting graves: "Visit the cemetery because it is a reminder of the hereafter. Remembering the hereafter will keep you from the evil and draw near to the good." ¹¹

Pilgrims strive to purify themselves both spiritually and physically through their prayers and religious practices. They feel that they have been relieved of their spiritual pain because of their sincere prayers to God. For many pilgrims, saints are a means of connecting them with Allah. The saints are their patron and God is their supporter. For this reason, visiting sacred places plays an important role in the lives of indigenous peoples. It is well known that the popularity of the sacred graves is determined by the prophecies of the saints buried there. If he had performed many miracles in the life of the saints, then his visit to the grave was considered to be crowded. The views of Islam on pilgrimage ceremonies have a long history. It is well-known that the rituals of pilgrimage have been around for a long time. This is especially evident in the mental state of the pilgrims.

¹⁰ Абрамзон С.М. Предметы культа казахов, киргизов и каракалпаков // Материальная культура и хозяйство народов Кавказа, Средней Азии и Казахстана. – Л.: Наука, 1978. – С. 56.

¹¹ Ислам энциклопедияси. – Т.: Узбекистон миллий энциклопедияси, 2004. – Б. 93.

In conclusion, it is important to note that the basic idea in the visions of the pilgrims is that they are sincere. That is why visiting the cemetery was the main criterion of the visit. The poet wrote that it is only possible to visit the mazar with a passion for it.¹² This is evident in every rite of the pilgrimage. Personal social calamities and misfortunes, especially childlessness, loss of loved ones, loss of life ideals, fear of sickness or death, loneliness and other social factors are important factors for people to visit the sanctuary as a result of their religious feelings. He does. For this reason, religious leaders and sheikhs in temples try to use the emotional state of pilgrims to influence their senses, while the role played by the sacred sites and myths related to the burials is important, but also enhances their attention to various rituals and ceremonies. This in turn, makes the place of pilgrimage more important in people's lives.¹³

There are sacred places, shrines in our country that are considered religious and national values. Actions in these areas also have their national, religious, psychological and historical roots. In-depth study of them will contribute to the spiritual development of the country, the elimination of some negative habits among the people, as well as the formation of positive traits and customs. It also serves to instill in the minds of the younger generation a healthy belief, a right outlook, and a love for the heritage of our ancestors. The southern oasis of Uzbekistan, the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya oasis, has experienced many historical events since ancient times. There are famous historical figures, scholars, saints, and Sufis in this country. Tombs and tombs were erected on their graves for their respect. Visiting the graves of the saints and graves is a good deed in Islam. Attending and respecting pilgrims is a religious value. In addition, pilgrimages and pilgrimages are one of the main ethnocultures of the Uzbek people, and they share the highest spiritual, moral and spiritual values, historical and cultural heritage.

¹² Абдулахатов Н., Хайдарова З., Азимов О. Биби Убайда тарихи. – Фаргона: Фаргона, 2002. – Б. 50.

¹³ Абдулахатов Н.У. Место паломничества в жизни населения Ферганской долины (по материалам святых мест Ферганского вилоята). Автореф. Дис. ...канд. Ист. Наук. – Т.: Институт истории АН РУз, 2008. – С. 12

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